

Variational symmetries and Conservation Laws,for Soliton equations in (2+1) Dimentions

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Abstract

In this paper,we study Variational symmetries and Conservation Laws ,and we obtain a direct relationship between Variational symmetries and Conservation Laws of the potential modified Korteweg-de Vries and the sin -Gorden equations , K.P.equation, and equaion of higher order

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1 Introduction

To find conservation laws we showed that it is fruitful if one examines . Consider Euclidean space , with $x = R^p$, with coordinate $x = (x^1, \dots, x^p)$ representing the independent variables , and $U = R^q$ with coordinate $u = (u^1, \dots, u^q)$ the dependent variables , let $\Omega \subset x$ be an open , connected subset with smooth boundary $\delta\Omega$, a Variational problem consists of a functional transformations which leave the action integral

$$J[u] = \int_{\Omega} L(x, u^n) dx$$

Invariant [1, 8,9] where L is called Euler -Lagrangian equation . we establish a direct relationship between invariances and conservation laws we obtain a direct relationship between Variational symmetries and Conservation Laws of the K-dV equations and the S-G equation , Boussinesq equation , K.P. equaion following the recent works on higher order is seen as follows:

Consider a partial equation of the form

Definition 1.1 (*Variational symmetries*)

A transformation

$$x^* = x$$

$$u^* = u + \varepsilon \eta(x, u, u_1, \dots, u_p + 0\varepsilon^2)$$

is a Variational symmetries of integral $J[u]$, if for any $u(x)$ there exists some vector function

$$A(x, u, u_1, \dots, u_r)$$

of x , u and its derivatives to some finite order r , such that if u^k is the infinitesimal generator [2] of a variational symmetry of an action integral

$$U^k L = D_i A^i \tag{1}$$

Where

$$U^k = \eta^\nu \frac{\delta}{\delta u^\nu} + \eta_i^\nu \frac{\delta}{\delta u_{i_1}^\nu} + \dots + \eta_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_k} \frac{\delta}{\delta u_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_k}}$$

And

$$D_i = \frac{\delta}{\delta x_i} + u_i \frac{\delta}{\delta u} + u_{i_j} \frac{\delta}{\delta u_{i_j}} + \dots$$

Holds for any $u(x)$, then [1,2] the conservation law

$$D_i [(W_i[u, \eta]) - A^i] = 0 \tag{2}$$

Holds for any solution $u(x)$ of Euler- Lagrange equation $E_y(L) = 0$, $\nu = 1, \dots, m$ where

$$W^i[u, \eta] = \eta^\nu \left[\frac{\delta L}{\delta u^\nu} - D_{i_1} \frac{\delta}{\delta u_{i_1}^\nu} + (-1)^{k-1} D_{i_1} D_{i_{k-1}} \frac{\delta L}{\delta u_{i_1 \dots i_{k-1}}} \right]$$

2 Examples

We give some examples to make use of this formulism and obtain conservation law for some Soliton equations.

Exempl (1) the Sin-Gorden equation

let Sin- Gorden equaion [4,5] is

$$u_{1t} - \sin u = 0$$

Consider

$$L = -\frac{1}{2} u_1 u_t + \cos u$$

and

$$\eta = [u_{111} + \frac{1}{2}u_1^3]$$

The corresponding Euler - Lagrange equation to Sin - Gorden equation here is

$$\begin{aligned} U^2L &= -\frac{1}{2}D_t(u_1\eta) + \frac{1}{2}u_{1t}\eta - \frac{1}{2}D_1(u_1\eta) + \frac{1}{2}u_{1t}\eta - \sin u\eta \\ U^2L &= -\frac{1}{2}u_1[u_{111t} + \frac{3}{2}u_1^2u_{1t}] - \frac{1}{2}u_t[u_{1111} + \frac{3}{2}u_1^2u_{11}] \\ &\quad - \sin u[u_{111} + \frac{1}{2}u_1^3] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Form (1) $U^2L = D_1A^1 + D_2A^2$ where A^1 and A^2 are vector functions of (x, u) and its derivatives then from (3)

$$\begin{aligned} A^1 &= \{-\frac{1}{2}u_t(u_{111} + u_1^3) - u_{11}u_{1t} - u_{11}\sin u + \frac{1}{2}\cos u\} \\ A^2 &= \{-\frac{1}{2}u_1u_{111} - \frac{3}{8}u_1^4 + \frac{1}{2}u_{11}^2\} \end{aligned}$$

from (2)

$$U^2L = -\frac{1}{2}u_1D_t\eta - \frac{1}{2}D_1\eta - \sin u\eta$$

Consequently

$$\begin{aligned} U^2L &= Eu\eta + D_1W^1[u, \eta] + D_tW^2[u, \eta] \\ EL(\eta) &= \frac{1}{2}U_{1t} - \sin u \\ &= u_{1t} - \sin u \end{aligned}$$

and

$$W^1 = -\frac{1}{2}u_t\eta, W^2 = -\frac{1}{2}u_1\eta$$

Now applying the conservation law (2) first

$$\begin{aligned} &D_1(W^1 - A^1) \\ &= [u_{111}u_{1t} - u_{111}\sin u + u_1u_{11}\cos u - u_1u_{11}\cos u - \frac{1}{2}u_1^2\sin u] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

And

$$D_t(W^2 - A^2) = D_t[-\frac{1}{2}u_{11}^2 + \frac{1}{8}u_1^4] - u_1u_{11t} + \frac{1}{2}u_1^3u_{1t} \quad (5)$$

Then from (4) , (5) the conservation law becomes

$$[u_{111} + \frac{1}{2}u_1^3][u_{1t} - \sin u] = 0$$

Example (2) K.d.V equation

Let K. d .V equation[3,4] is

$$V_{xxx} + VV_x + V_t = 0$$

Let

$$V = u_x = u_1$$

Then

$$u_{xxxx} + u_x u_{xx} + u_{xt} = 0$$

Then the transformed is

$$u_{1111} + u_1 u_{11} + u_{1t} = 0$$

Which is the Euler -Lagrange equation for

$$L = \frac{1}{2}u_{11}^2 - \frac{1}{6}u_1^3 - \frac{1}{2}u_1 u_t$$

Let U^2 be twice extended operator of

$$U = \eta \frac{\delta}{\delta u}$$

Where

$$U^2 L = EL\eta + D_1 W^1[u_1\eta] + D_t W^2[u_t\eta]$$

then

$$U^2 L = u_{11} D_1^2 \eta - \frac{1}{2} u_1^2 D_1 \eta - \frac{1}{2} u_t D_1 \eta$$

consequently , where

$$EL = u_{1111} + u_1 u_{11} + u_{1t}$$

$$W^1[u, \eta] = u_{11} D_1 \eta - u_{111} \eta - \frac{1}{2} u_1^2 \eta - \frac{1}{2} u_t \eta$$

$$W^2[u, \eta] = \frac{1}{2}(u, \eta)$$

and determined

$$A^1 = t[\frac{1}{2}u_{11}^2 - \frac{1}{6}u_1^3 - \frac{1}{2}u_1 u_t]$$

$$A^2 = \frac{1}{2}u$$

$$\eta = (tu_1 - x)$$

Then we obtain the conservation law

$$D_1(W^1 - A^1) + D_t(W^2 - A^2) = 0$$

wich we can calculate as :

$$D_1(W^1 - A^1) = D_1[u_{11} D_1(tu_1 - x) - u_{111}(tu_1 - x) - \frac{1}{2}u_1^2(tu_1 - x) - \frac{1}{2}u_t(tu_1 - x)]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -D_1 t \left[\frac{1}{2} u_{11}^2 - \frac{1}{6} u_1^3 - \frac{1}{2} u_1 u_t \right] \\
= & D_1 \left[t u_{11}^2 - u_{11} - t u_{111} u_1 + x u_{111} - \frac{1}{2} t u_1^3 + \frac{1}{2} x u_1^2 - t u_1 u_t + \frac{1}{2} x u_t - \frac{1}{2} t u_{11}^2 + \frac{1}{6} t u_1^3 + \frac{1}{2} t u_1 u_t \right] \\
= & D_1 \left[t \left(-\frac{1}{2} u_{11}^2 - \frac{1}{3} - u_1 u_{111} \right) - u_{11} + x u_{111} + \frac{1}{2} x (u_1^2 + u_2) \right]
\end{aligned}$$

D is total derivative respect to x

$$\begin{aligned}
D_t(W^1 - A^1) &= (t u_{11} u_{111} - t u_1^2 u_{11} - t u_1 u_{111}) \\
& - t u_{11} u_{111} - u_{111} + u_{111} + x u_1 u_{11} + \frac{1}{2} u_t + \frac{1}{2} x u_{1t} + x u_{1111} + \frac{1}{2} u_t^2
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

And D_t is defined analogously. Without loss of generality, we assume that η does depend on t - derivatives since for admissible operators can always eliminated using equation (1)

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
D_t(W^2 - A^2) &= D_t \left(-\frac{1}{2} u_1 (t u_1 - x) - \frac{1}{2} u \right) \\
&= D_t \left[-\frac{1}{2} t u_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} x u_1 - \frac{1}{2} u \right] \\
&= \left[-\frac{1}{2} u_1^2 - t u_1 u_{1t} - \frac{1}{2} u_t \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

From (6) and (7) we obtain the conservation law, which here become

$$\begin{aligned}
D_1(W^1 - A^1) + D_t(W^2 - A^2) &= 0 \\
= -t u_1 (u_{1111} + u_1 u_{11} + u_{1t}) + x (u_{1111} + u_1 u_{11} + u_{1t}) &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

3 conservation laws for Boussinesq equation

We illustrate here equation of higher order to obtain higher order [6,7] conservation laws for Boussinesq equation

let

$$u_{tt} + 2u u_{xx} + 2u_x^2 + u_{xxxx} = 0$$

The transformed Boussinesq equation is

$$u_{1111} + 2u u_{11} + 2u_1^2 + u_{tt} = 0$$

Wich is Euler - Lagrange equation

$$L = \frac{1}{2} u_{11}^2 - u u_1^2 - \frac{1}{2} u_t^2$$

Let U^2 be twice extended operator then

$$U^2 L = u_{11} D_1^2 \eta - 2u u_1 D_1 \eta - u_t D_t \eta$$

Where

$$U^2 L = EL\eta + D_1 W^1[u, \eta] + D_t W^2[u, \eta]$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} EL &= u_{1111} + 2u_1^2 + 2uu_{11} + u_{1t} \\ W^1[u, \eta] &= u_{11}D_1\eta + u_{111}\eta - 2uu_1\eta \\ W^2[u, \eta] &= -[u_t, \eta] \end{aligned}$$

Then we obtain the coservation law () Where

$$D_1(W^1 - A^1) = [-tu_1^3 + tu_t u_{1t} - tu_1 u_{1111} + xu_{1111} - 2tuu_1 u_{11} + 2xu_1^2 + xu_1 u_{11}] \quad (8)$$

$$D_t(W^2 - A^2) = D_t[-u_t[tu_1 - x] - u] \quad (9)$$

Thus from (8) and (9) the coservation law:

$$\begin{aligned} D_1(W^1 - A^1) + D_t(W^2 - A^2) &= -tu_1[u_{1111} + 2u_1^2 + 2uu_{11} + u_{tt}] \\ &+ x[u_{1111} + 2u_1^2 + 2uu_{11} + u_{tt}] = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Where

$$[u_{1111} + 2u_1^2 + 2uu_{11} + u_{tt}] = 0$$

4 in the 3- dimensional case of K.P. equation

We take one of higher dimensional equations,[4 ,5] called the Kadomtsev - Petviashvili K . P. equation to get the relation between variational symmetry and coservation law which is written as

$$D_1(W^1 - A^1) + D_t(W^2 - A^2) - D_y(W^3 - A^3) = 0 \quad (10)$$

in the 3- dimensional case of K.P. equation

Consider K.P. equation as

$$(u_{xxx} + \frac{1}{2}u_x^2)_x + \sigma u_{yy} = 0$$

Where σ is a constant , $\sigma = \pm 1$

Then the transformed *K.P.* equation is

$$u_{1111} + u_1 u_{11} + u_{1t} + \sigma u_y^2$$

is the Euler - Lagrange equation for Lagrangian L

$$L = \frac{1}{2}u_{11}^2 - \frac{1}{6}u_1^3 - \frac{1}{2}u_1 u_t - \frac{1}{2}\sigma u_y^2$$

Let U^2 be twice extended operator of $U = \eta \frac{\delta}{\delta u}$ Then

$$U^2 L = u_{11}D_1^2\eta - \frac{1}{2}u_1^2 D_1\eta - \frac{1}{2}u_1 D_t\eta - \frac{1}{2}u_t D_1\eta - \sigma u_y D_y\eta$$

where

$$U^2L = EL\eta + D_1W^1[u, \eta] + D_tW^2[u, \eta] + D_yW^3[u, \eta]$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} EL &= u_{1111} + u_1u_{11} + u_{1t} + \sigma u_{yy} = 0 \\ W^1[u, \eta] &= u_{11}D_1\eta - u_{111}\eta - \frac{1}{2}\eta[u_1^2 + u_t] \\ W^2[u, \eta] &= -\frac{1}{2}[u_1\eta] \\ W^3[u, \eta] &= -[\sigma u_y\eta] \end{aligned}$$

And determined

$$\begin{aligned} A^1 &= t[\frac{1}{2}u_{11}^2 - \frac{1}{6}u_1^3 - \frac{1}{2}u_1u_t - \frac{1}{2}\sigma u_y^2] \\ A^2 &= \frac{1}{2}u \\ A^3 &= \sigma u \\ \eta &= (tu - x - y) \end{aligned}$$

Then we obtain the coservation law which becomes

$$\begin{aligned} D_1(w^1 - A^1) &= D_1[u_{11}D_1(tu_1 - x - y) - u_{111}(tu_1 - x - y) - \frac{1}{2}u_1^2(tu_1 - x - y) - \frac{1}{2}u_t(tu_1 - x - y)] \\ &\quad - D_1t[\frac{1}{2}u_{11}^2 - \frac{1}{6}u_1^3 - \frac{1}{2}u_1u_t - \sigma u_y^2] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$D_t[W_2 - A^2] = D_t[\frac{1}{2}u_1(tu_1 - x - y) - \frac{1}{2}u] \quad (12)$$

$$D_y[W^3 - A^3] = D_y[-\sigma u_y(tu_1 - x - y) - \sigma u] \quad (13)$$

from (11) , (12) ,(13)we obtain the conservation law which here become

$$\begin{aligned} &D_1(W^1 - A^1) + D_t(W^2 - A^2) - D_y(W^3 - A^3) \\ &= xu_{1111} + yu_{1111} - tu_1^2u_{11} + xu_1u_{11} \\ &\quad - tu_1u_{1111} + yu_{1t} + yu_1u_{11} + \frac{1}{2}xu_{1t} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2}yu_{1t} - tu_1u_{1t} + \frac{1}{2}xu_{1t} + \frac{1}{2}yu_{1t} - \sigma tu_1u_{yy} + \sigma xu_{yy} + \sigma yu_{yy} \end{aligned}$$

So we get

$$u_{1111} + u_1u_{11} + u_{1t} + \sigma u_{yy} = 0$$

And the conservation law is (10)

$$\begin{aligned} &D_1(W^1 - A^1) + D_t(W^2 - A^2) - D_y(W^3 - A^3) \\ &= -tu_1[u_{1111} + u_1u_{11} + u_{1t} + \sigma u_{yy}] \\ &\quad + x[u_{1111} + u_1u_{11} + u_{1t} + \sigma u_{yy}] \\ &\quad + y[u_{1111} + u_1u_{11} + u_{1t} + \sigma u_{yy}] = 0 \end{aligned}$$

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